

Preparation and Characterization of Herbal Wine from *Aloe vera* L. (Sha Zaung Let Pat) Gel

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Abstract

Aloe vera gel contains many phytonutrients and anti-oxidant compounds, which help support the health of immune system. In this research work, *Aloe vera* gel was used with sugar as a substrate for the production of fermented *Aloe vera* based herbal wine. *Aloe vera* samples were collected from Pakokku University Campus, Pakokku Township, Magway Region. The quality of *Aloe vera* wine was observed by judging from the acceptability of color, clarity, aroma, flavor of the finished product by panel sensory evaluation. Then, the physicochemical properties of *Aloe vera* wine were studied. The pH (3.8), alcohol content (8 %), acidity value (4.875 g/L), sugar content (3.5 %) and protein content (0.18 %) were found in prepared herbal wine. Moreover, antimicrobial activities of the prepared herbal wine were also investigated by using Agar well diffusion method. The herbal wine responded high activities on all tested microorganisms.

Keywords: Wine, *Aloe vera*, Physicochemical properties, Antimicrobial Activities

Introduction

Wine has been produced for thousands of years. The earliest known evidence of wine comes from Georgia, where 8000 year old wine jars were found. Wine has long played an important role in religion. It is an alcoholic beverage made from fermented fruits such as grapes, apples, pomegranates and berries which are generally called fruit wine. Other wines, such as barley wine, rice wine and medicinal wine can also be made. Barely wine and rice wine are made from starch-based materials and resemble beer more than wine. Medicinal wine is having medicinal properties, usually prepared wines contain many chemical compounds similar or identical to those in fruits, vegetable and spices with the incorporation of herbs and medicinal plants (Vaishali, 2018). Wines are classified depending upon various attributes such as chemical composition of juice, use of additives, vinification techniques and aging of wine, the alcohol and sugar content. All wines can be organized into five fundamental groups. Within each group there are hundreds of different varieties and also different wine making styles.

Aloe vera Linn (Sha-Zaung-let-pat) is a native of North Africa and Spain. It has spread to Myanmar, India, China and topical countries. *Aloe vera* is widely distributed in Myanmar. The ten main areas of chemical constituents of *Aloe vera* include: amino acids, anthraquinones, enzymes, minerals, vitamins, lignins, monosaccharide, polysaccharides, salicylic acid, saponins and sterols. *Aloe vera* has been used for medicinal purposes in several cultures. Although use of *Aloe vera* may have significant health benefits, some side effects may come after prolonged use.

Beverage made with *Aloe vera* juice possesses natural detoxifying properties that effectively cleanse the digestive system and the circulatory system. As the absorption level of nutrients accelerates, it results in better blood circulation and also improves health. When the blood is oxygen-rich, it automatically provides nutrients within the cells more proficiently. These healthy cells ensure body's ability to ward off infections, strengthening immune system.

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Its rejuvenating properties work within body to keep it fresh and active throughout the day. Regular consumption of *Aloe vera* wine is very helpful in weight loss. This stimulates digestive tract functioning as a laxative. Drinking *Aloe vera* wine brings refreshment to the body, energy level increases and weight loss (Sharrif *et al.*, 2011).

Materials and Methods

Preparation of Sample

In this research, *Aloe vera* leaves were collected from Pakokku University Campus, Pakokku Township, Magway Region. *Aloe vera* leaves were washed with water and the lower 1 inch of the leaf base the tapering point 2 inches of the leaf top and the short sharp spines located along the leaf margins were removed by a sharp knife. The colorless gel contained in the inner part of the fresh leaves was extracted. It was cut to small pieces. Finally, *Aloe vera* gel samples were obtained for the winemaking.

Figure (1) *Aloe vera* Leaves

Figure (2) *Aloe vera* gel

Preparation of *Aloe Vera* Wine

(200) g of *Aloe vera* gel was weighed and placed in a blender containing (120) g of sugar and (600) mL of distilled water. This mixture was blended on high speed for one minute to obtain the juice extract. Then, *Aloe vera* juice was transferred to a steel pot and boiled at 80°C for 10 minutes on hot plate. This juice was cooled and poured into the bottle and then added (0.5) g of yeast, (1) g of diammonium phosphate and (0.24) g of preservative mix together. This solution was fermented for three weeks into the dark room. After that, fermented *Aloe vera* solution was racked, storing and aging for one week. Finally, *Aloe vera* wine was obtained.

Figure (3) Herbal wine prepared from *Aloe Vera* gel

Physicochemical Properties of Herbal Wine

Determination of pH

A herbal wine was placed in 100 mL beaker. The electrode was rinsed with distilled water and cleaned with soft tissue paper. Before measuring, the pH meter was calibrated by using pH 7 buffer solution. Then, the electrode of pocket pH meter was placed in the beaker containing herbal wine and read the pH immediately.

Determination of Alcohol (%)

The alcohol meter was rinsed with distilled water and cleaned with soft tissue paper. Then, the alcohol meter was placed in the measuring cylinder containing herbal wine (100) mL and read the alcohol (%).

Determination of Acidity Value

25 mL of the herbal wine was placed in a beaker and evaporated on a boiling water bath for 30 seconds to remove the carbon dioxide from prepared wine. Then, the herbal wine was swirled, cooled and used for titration from this degassed portion of wine. 10 mL of herbal wine was pipetted out in a clean conical flask and added 10 mL of hot distilled water. Then 2 drops of phenolphthalein indicator was introduced into the sample solution. This mixture was stirred and titrated with 0.1 M of sodium hydroxide solution until a light pink colour persists. Then the value of acidity was calculated.

Determination of Sugar and Protein Contents

The sugar content of herbal wine was directly measured by using refractometer and protein content was determined by Kjeldahl method.

Antimicrobial Activities of Herbal Wine

In-vitro antimicrobial activity determinations of the herbal wine was carried out by using agar well diffusion method. In this experiment, seven microorganisms such as

Agrobacterium tumefaciens, *Bacillus pumilus*, *Bacillus subtilis*, *Candida albicans*, *Escherichia coli*, *Pseudomonas fluorescens* and *Staphylococcus aureus* were selected.

Results and Discussion

Physicochemical Properties of Herbal Wine

pH Value of Herbal Wine

The pH of wine plays a critical role in many aspects of winemaking in particular wine stability. It is a measure of the strength and concentration of the dissociated acids present in that medium. Wines are more stable at lower pH. In this research, pH values of the *Aloe vera* wine was studied by using pocket pH meter. The pH value was observed 3.8 in herbal wine. According to the literature, most of the wine have pH value between 3.0 and 4.0.

Alcohol (%) of Herbal Wine

Different wines have varying levels of alcohol content. In modern times, there have become more efficient ways to make wine that allow higher alcohol content. In this research, alcohol (%) of herbal wine was studied by using alcohol meter. The alcohol content of herbal wine was 8%. So, alcohol (%) of *Aloe vera* wine has acceptable limit of EAC standard (6.5-16.5%).

Acidity (Tartaric acid) Content of Herbal Wine

The acid in wines are important component in both winemaking and the finished product of wine. They are present in wine, having direct influence on the colour, balance and taste of the wine as well as the growth and vitality of yeast during fermentation and protecting the wine from bacteria. In this research, acidity content of herbal wine was studied by using titration method. The acidity content of prepared wine was 4.875 g/L. The acidity content of wines in EAC standard value are in the range of (4-12 g/L).

Sugar Content of Herbal Wine

Sugar content in wine is usually a measure of residual sugars left behind during the fermentation process. Higher alcohol wines have less sugar and lower alcohol wines have more sugar. In this research, sugar content of herbal wine was 3.5 %. The lower sugar content in the end product might have been during to the fermentation of wine. Sugar content of herbal wine has acceptable limit of EAC standard (<4 %).

Protein Content of Herbal Wine

Proteins are typically present in wines in low concentrations, contributing little to their nutritive value. However, they assume a considerable technological and economical important because they greatly affect the clarity and stability of wines. In this research, protein content of herbal wine was 0.18 %.

Table (1) Results of Physicochemical Properties of Herbal Wine

No.	Parameter	Herbal Wine	EAC Standard
1	pH	3.8	-
2	Alcohol (%)	8	6.5-16.5
3	Acidity content (gL ⁻¹)	4.875	4-12
5	Sugar content (%)	3.5	< 4.0
6	Protein content (%)	0.18	-

*EAC – East African Community

Antimicrobial Activities of Herbal Wine

The antimicrobial activities of herbal wine were detected by using Agar Well Diffusion method. The results of this detection would be seen in Table (2) and Figure (5). According to this table, the microorganisms were observed that herbal wine from *Aloe vera* have high activities on all tested microorganisms such as *Agrobacterium tumefaciens*, *Bacillus pumilus*, *Bacillus subtilis*, *Candida albicans*, *Escherichia coli*, *Pseudomonas fluorescens* and *Staphylococcus aureus*.

Table (2) Results for Antimicrobial Activity of Herbal Wine on Seven Microorganisms

No.	Microorganisms	Herbal Wine	Diseases
1.	<i>Agrobacterium tumefaciens</i>	+++	Crown gall tumour
2.	<i>Bacillus pumilus</i>	+++	Eye infection
3.	<i>Bacillus subtilis</i>	+++	Anthrax
4.	<i>Candida albicans</i>	+++	Fungal infection
5.	<i>Escherichia coli</i>	+++	Diarrhea
6.	<i>Pseudomonas fluorescens</i>	+++	Chronic diseases
7.	<i>Staphylococcus aureus</i>	+++	Abscess

Agar well – 8 mm

8 mm – 12 mm (+)

13 mm – 17mm (++)

18 mm above (+++)

(+) – low activity

(++) – medium activity

(+++) – high activity

Figure (4) Effects of herbal wine on Seven Microorganisms

Conclusion

In this research, *Aloe vera* based herbal wine was prepared. After one month fermentation time, prepared wine was obtained for investigating. Then, physicochemical properties of prepared wine from *Aloe vera* was determined. From the determination, the value of pH was found to be 3.8. The alcohol (%) of herbal wine was 8 %. Alcohol (%) of herbal wine has acceptable limit of EAC standard (6.5-16.5%). The acidity value of prepared wine from *Aloe vera* was 4.87 gL⁻¹. Acids affect the taste and mouth-feel of wine. Acidity value of herbal wine has acceptable limit of EAC standard. Sugar is known as the most important raw material during fermentation process. Sugar content in *Aloe vera* wine is 3.5 %. This value was acceptable limit of EAC standard (<4 %). Small amount of protein content was also observed in prepared herbal wine. The antimicrobial activities of herbal wine prepared from *Aloe vera* gel was determined by using Agar Well Diffusion method. Seven selected microorganisms were tested in this research. Herbal wine responded high activities on all tested microorganisms. It was observed that herbal wine has high activity to prevent several infection. According to this results, herbal wine prepared from *Aloe vera* has many health benefits.

Acknowledgements

I would like to thank Rector Dr Aye Aye Tun and Pro-rector Dr Yin Yin Than, Bago University for their permissions to carry out this research. I also wish to thank Professor Dr Aye Aye Cho, Head of Department of Chemistry, Bago University for kind permission to submit this paper. I am also grateful to express Dr Mya Thu Zar, Professor, Department of Chemistry, Bago University for her encouragement and advice.

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